

Study	Early or Late Onset	n	Prevalence of sepsis (%)	Timing of test	PCT Cut-off (ng/mL)	Inclusion Criteria	Diagnosis of sepsis	Sensitivity	Specificity	LR+	LR-	DOR	Ln(DOR)	St error (ln(DOR))
<i>Adib 2012</i>	Early and Late	69	29	0h	1.15	Suspected sepsis	MC	0.700	0.400	1.2	0.75	1.6	0.44	0.57
<i>Bender 2008</i>	Early	123	24	0h	5.75	Suspected sepsis	MC or CR	0.690	0.670	2.1	0.46	4.5	1.51	0.46
					25			0.207	0.926	2.8	0.86	3.2	1.18	0.60
<i>Bonac 2000</i>	Early	58	15	0h	9.98	Suspected sepsis	MC or CR	0.520	0.910	5.8	0.53	11.0	2.39	0.83
				24h	13.03			0.590	0.820	3.3	0.50	6.6	1.88	0.77
				48h	3.07			0.500	1.000	2450.5	0.50	4900.0	8.50	10.02
<i>Boo 2008</i>	Early and Late	87	21	0h	0.5	Suspected Sepsis	MC	0.889	0.406	1.5	0.27	5.5	1.70	0.79
				12-24 h	2			0.889	0.652	2.6	0.17	15.0	2.71	0.79
				36-48 h	10			0.722	0.754	2.9	0.37	8.0	2.07	0.60
<i>Groselj-Grenc 2009</i>	Early and Late	46	63	0h	2.28	SIRS	MC or CR	0.824	0.483	1.6	0.37	4.4	1.47	0.74
				24h	5.55			0.313	1.000	906.6	0.69	1318.2	7.18	10.02
<i>Guibourdenche 2002</i>	Early	120	18	0-72h	2.5	Suspected sepsis	MC or CR	0.857	0.898	8.4	0.16	52.7	3.96	0.72
<i>Koskenvuo 2003</i>	Early	22	22	12 h	2	SIRS	MC or CR	0.998	0.176	1.2	0.01	107.1	4.67	10.03
<i>Lopez Sastre 2006</i>	Late	100	61	0 h	0.59	Suspected sepsis	MC	0.820	0.795	4.0	0.23	17.6	2.87	0.52
				12-24 h	1.34			0.869	0.718	3.1	0.18	16.9	2.83	0.52
				36-48 h	0.69			0.738	0.795	3.6	0.33	10.9	2.39	0.49
<i>Naher 2011</i>	Early and Late	50	80	0h	0.5	Suspected Sepsis	MC or CR	0.900	0.550	2.0	0.18	11.0	2.40	1.10
<i>Resch 2003</i>	Early	68	61	0h	2	Suspected Sepsis	MC or CR	0.830	0.610	2.1	0.28	7.6	2.03	0.57
					6			0.770	0.910	8.6	0.25	33.9	3.52	0.77
					14			0.630	1.000	1701.6	0.37	4597.3	8.43	10.01
<i>Sakha 2008</i>	Early and Late	117	23	-	2.5	Suspected sepsis	MC	0.667	0.500	1.3	0.67	2.0	0.69	0.46
<i>Schlapbach 2013</i>	Early	137	24.1	0 h	2	Suspected sepsis	MC or CR	0.879	0.510	1.8	0.24	7.5	2.02	0.57
<i>Vazzalwar 2004</i>	Late	51	35.3	0 h	0.5	Suspected sepsis	MC or CR	0.944	0.364	1.5	0.15	9.7	2.27	1.09
					1			0.778	0.636	2.1	0.35	6.1	1.81	0.67
<i>Zahedpasha 2009</i>	Early and Late	38	28.9	0 h	0.5	Suspected sepsis	MC or CR	0.999	0.259	1.3	0.00	385.0	5.95	10.01
					2			0.999	0.333	1.5	0.00	550.0	6.31	10.01
					10			0.909	0.852	6.1	0.11	57.5	4.05	1.18